

Customer Perception Towards Online Marketing in E-Commerce: A Study on Products, Pricing, Delivery and Service Quality of Amazon, Flipkart and Meesho in Thiruvvarur District

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to examine customers' opinions about e-commerce marketing on Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho. The research focuses on product quality, the price, delivery efficiency, and the excellence of service. Customers' likes and satisfaction were examined by researchers from 100 surveys. The results show that Amazon is regarded as the best when it comes to product quality, dependability, and safe packing. However, Customers use it less frequently. The most popular platform among respondents, however, is Flipkart. This is mostly because of its quicker delivery, reasonable costs, attractive offers, and increased customer satisfaction. Its improved service quality and successful delivery method greatly improve the customer experience. Meesho attracts customers due to its low pricing, especially among price-sensitive users. However, its product quality and service performance are comparatively lower, which negatively affects overall customer satisfaction. As a result, Amazon stands out for its greater quality and dependability, while Flipkart leads in terms of usability and customer satisfaction. While Meesho excels in pricing, it falls short when it comes to quality and customer service.

Keywords: Customer Perception, Customer Satisfaction, E-Commerce, Online Marketing, Service Quality.

1. Introduction

Customer perception towards online marketing has become one of the most important areas of study in the present digital era. The rapid development of internet technology and the increasing use of smartphones have significantly changed the buying behaviour of consumers. Customers are now shifting from traditional shopping methods to online platforms due to convenience, time-saving nature, wide product availability, and attractive offers. As a result, e-commerce has emerged as a powerful tool in modern business, transforming the way products and services are marketed and delivered. Customer satisfaction in e-commerce platforms mainly depends on several key factors such as product quality, pricing strategy, delivery performance, return and refund policies, customer service, and overall user experience. Online marketing plays a major role in influencing customer decisions by providing detailed product information, discounts, reviews, and comparison options. Therefore, understanding customer perception towards these factors is essential for improving service quality and maintaining competitiveness in the market. In India,

the growth of e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho has been remarkable. These platforms have created a strong presence in both urban and rural areas by offering a wide range of products including electronics, clothing, home appliances, beauty products, and books. Amazon is known for its global standards and reliable service, Flipkart is widely recognized for its customer-friendly policies and strong domestic reach, while Meesho has gained popularity for its low-cost reselling model and affordability. Each platform has its own strengths and weaknesses, which directly influence customer perception and satisfaction levels. Customer preferences are influenced by various demographic factors such as age, occupation, income level, and place of residence. Younger generations, especially students and working professionals, are more engaged in online shopping due to their familiarity with digital technology. Similarly, middle-income groups tend to use e-commerce platforms more frequently because of competitive pricing and discount offers. The accessibility of internet services in semi-urban and rural areas has also contributed to the growth of online shopping behaviour. In

this context, the present study focuses on analysing customer perception towards online marketing in e-commerce with special reference to Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho in Thiruvavur District. The study examines various aspects such as product preference, pricing satisfaction, delivery performance, service quality, and problems faced by customers. It also evaluates the level of satisfaction and willingness of customers to recommend these platforms to others. The findings of this study will be useful for e-commerce companies to understand customer expectations and improve their services accordingly. It will also help in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of different platforms, thereby providing valuable suggestions for enhancing customer satisfaction and improving overall online marketing strategies.

2. Objectives

- To study the level of awareness of customers about online marketing in e-commerce platforms.
- To analyze the preference of customers towards different e-commerce websites such as Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho.
- To examine the factors influencing customers to choose online shopping over traditional shopping.
- To evaluate customer satisfaction with respect to product quality, pricing, and discounts offered by e-commerce platforms.
- To study the delivery performance and timeliness of different online shopping platforms.
- To analyze the effectiveness of return and refund policies provided by e-commerce companies.
- To assess the quality of customer support services offered by these platforms.
- To identify the common problems faced by customers while shopping online.
- To measure the overall satisfaction level of customers towards e-commerce services.
- To understand the willingness of customers to recommend these platforms to others

3. Research Methodology

The present study aims to analyse customer perception towards online marketing in e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho in Thiruvavur District. The study focuses on various factors influencing customer satisfaction, including product quality, pricing, delivery performance, service quality, customer support, and return policies.

Research Design

The study is based on a descriptive research design. Descriptive research is used to describe the

characteristics, opinions, and behaviour of customers regarding online shopping platforms. It helps in understanding customer preferences and satisfaction levels towards e-commerce services.

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Thiruvavur District, Tamil Nadu. Respondents from urban, semi-urban, and rural areas were included to obtain a broader understanding of customer perception towards online marketing.

Sources of Data

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study.

Primary Data:

Primary data were collected directly from customers through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire included questions relating to customer preference, pricing satisfaction, delivery services, product quality, discounts, return policies, customer support, and overall satisfaction towards Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data were collected from books, journals, research articles, company websites, annual reports, magazines, and various online sources related to e-commerce and digital marketing.

Sampling Technique

The study adopted the Non-Probability Convenience Sampling Method. Respondents who were easily accessible and willing to participate in the survey were selected for data collection.

Sample Size

A total of 100 respondents were selected for the study from different occupational and income groups in Thiruvavur District.

Period of the Study

The study was conducted over a period of eighty days during January 2025.

Tools for Analysis

The collected data were classified, tabulated, and analysed using percentage analysis and simple table interpretation methods. The analysis helped in identifying customer opinions, satisfaction levels, and preferences towards different e-commerce platforms.

Limitations of the Study

- The study is limited to Thiruvavur District only.
- The sample size is restricted to 100 respondents.
- The study is based on the opinions and perceptions of respondents, which may vary over time.

- Time and cost constraints limited the scope of detailed analysis.
- The findings may not represent the views of all online customers in other regions.

3. Company Profile

Amazon

Amazon is one of the largest e-commerce companies in the world. It was founded by Jeff Bezos in the year 1994 in the United States. The company initially started as an online bookstore, operating from a small garage. Over time, Amazon expanded its business into selling a wide variety of products such as electronics, clothing, home appliances, books, and many more. Amazon officially launched its website in 1995 and quickly gained popularity due to its convenience and wide product selection. The company introduced several innovations such as customer reviews, personalized recommendations, and fast delivery services. One of its major services, Amazon Prime, offers benefits like faster delivery, streaming, and exclusive deals. Amazon entered the Indian market in 2013 and has since become one of the leading online shopping platforms in the country. It is well known for its reliable service, good packaging, easy return policies, and strong customer support. The company focuses on customer satisfaction and continues to improve its services through technology and innovation.

Flipkart

Flipkart is one of India's leading e-commerce companies. It was founded by Sachin Bansal and Binny Bansal in 2007. Both founders were former employees of Amazon and started Flipkart as an online bookstore

in India. In its early stages, Flipkart focused on selling books and gradually expanded into other product categories such as electronics, fashion, home appliances, and more. The company gained popularity due to its affordable pricing, attractive discounts, and innovative services like cash on delivery, which made online shopping easier for Indian customers. Flipkart introduced major sales events like the Big Billion Days, which attracted a large number of customers across the country. In 2018, Flipkart was acquired by Walmart, which further strengthened its position in the market. Today, Flipkart is known for its strong delivery network, customer-friendly return and refund policies, and good service quality. It has a wide reach in both urban and rural areas of India and continues to grow rapidly.

Meesho

Meesho is a fast-growing Indian e-commerce platform that mainly focuses on reselling and small businesses. It was founded in 2015 by Vidit Aatrey and Sanjeev Barnwal. The main aim of Meesho is to help individuals, especially women and small entrepreneurs, to start their own online business with zero investment. It allows users to sell products through social media platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram. Meesho offers a wide range of products, mainly focusing on clothing, accessories, and household items at low prices. The company has grown rapidly due to its simple business model and affordable product range. It is especially popular in semi-urban and rural areas where people look for budget-friendly products. However, compared to Amazon and Flipkart, Meesho sometimes faces challenges related to product quality and delivery services. Despite these challenges, Meesho continues to expand its market and support small sellers by providing them with a platform to grow their business.

4. Comparison of Amazon, Flipkart and Meesho.

Factors	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho
Founder	Jeff Bezos	Sachin & Binny	Vidit Aatrey and Sanjeev Barnwal
Year of Establishment	1994	2007	2015
Origin Country	USA	India	India
Product Range	Very wide	Wide	Limited (Mainly Clothing)
Pricing	Moderate	Affordable	Low price
Discounts	Good	Very High	Moderate
Delivery Speed	Fast	Fast	Moderate
Return & Refund	Easy	Very Easy	Moderate
Customer Support	Good	Very Good	Average
Popularity	Global	High in India	Growing in India
Best for	Quality and Variety	Offers and Service	Low-cost shopping

5. Review of Literature

Customer perception towards online marketing in e-commerce has attracted the attention of many researchers in recent years. The rapid growth of internet usage and smartphone penetration has changed the way consumers search, evaluate, and purchase products. Various studies have examined the factors influencing customer attitude and satisfaction in online shopping environments.

Philip Kotler (2017) stated that customer perception is a key element in marketing, as it directly affects consumer behaviour and decision-making. According to him, online marketing strategies such as product presentation, pricing, and promotion play an important role in shaping customer opinions. He also emphasized that companies must focus on creating value for customers to ensure long-term success.

Dave Chaffey (2018) explained that digital marketing has transformed traditional business practices by making information easily accessible to customers. His study highlights that convenience, time-saving, and the ability to compare products are the main reasons for the growth of e-commerce. He also noted that customers prefer platforms that provide user-friendly interfaces and smooth navigation.

Kenneth C. Laudon and Carol Traver (2020) discussed that e-commerce systems depend heavily on customer satisfaction and trust. Their research shows that factors such as website design, product availability, secure payment systems, and delivery services significantly influence customer perception. They pointed out that trust is built through consistent service quality and reliable transactions.

Usha Ramanathan (2019) focused on the importance of logistics and delivery performance in e-commerce. The study revealed that timely delivery and proper handling of goods increase customer satisfaction, while delays and damaged products create negative experiences. Efficient supply chain management was identified as a crucial factor for improving service quality.

Srinivasan S. (2017) highlighted that pricing strategies and discounts are major factors that attract customers to online platforms. The study found that customers often compare prices across multiple websites before making a purchase decision. Competitive pricing and seasonal discounts help in increasing customer engagement and sales.

David Gefen (2016) emphasized the role of trust in online shopping behaviour. According to his research, customers are more likely to use e-commerce platforms that provide secure payment options and clear return policies. Trust reduces perceived risk and encourages repeat purchases.

A. Parasuraman (2015) explained the concept of service quality and its impact on customer satisfaction. He stated that responsiveness, reliability, and assurance are key dimensions of service quality. In the context of e-commerce, quick customer support and effective problem-solving improve customer loyalty.

V. Kumar (2021) studied the influence of demographic factors on online shopping behaviour. The findings show that younger consumers, especially students and working professionals, are more active in online shopping. Income level and occupation also affect purchasing patterns and preferences.

Sunil Gupta (2020) analyzed the importance of product quality and customer reviews in e-commerce. The study found that positive reviews and high ratings increase customer confidence, while negative feedback discourages purchases. Customers rely heavily on the experiences of others before making decisions.

Neha Sharma (2022) identified the common problems faced by online shoppers, including late delivery, poor product quality, payment failures, and difficulties in return and refund processes. The study suggested that addressing these issues can improve customer satisfaction and build a positive brand image.

6. Analysis and Interpretation

1. Age.

Table No.1: Age- Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Below 20 Years	8	12	5	25	25 %
21-30 Years	12	15	8	35	35%
31-40 Years	7	9	4	20	20%
41-50 Years	5	6	2	13	13%
51-60 Years	2	2	1	5	5%
Above 61 Years	1	1	0	2	2%
Total	35	45	20	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 1, it is clearly understood that the majority of respondents (35%) belong to the age group of 21–30 years, followed by 25% below 20 years. This shows that younger people are more actively involved in online shopping due to better awareness and technology usage. The participation of older age groups is comparatively low. Among the platforms, Flipkart has slightly higher usage across most age categories, indicating its popularity among youth.

2. Occupation.

Table No.2: Occupation- wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Agriculture	5	7	3	15	15%
Business	5	8	2	15	15%
Government Job	5	4	1	10	10%
Private Job	8	10	4	22	22%
Student	9	14	7	30	30%
Others	2	4	2	8	8%
Total	34	47	19	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 2, it is observed that students (30%) form the largest portion of respondents, followed by private employees (22%). This indicates that individuals who are more exposed to digital platforms prefer online shopping. Business people and agriculture workers also show moderate participation. Flipkart is more preferred among students and private employees, showing its strong reach among active customers.

3. Monthly Income.

Table No.2: Occupation- wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Below 20000 Rs	3	2	5	10	10%
21000-30000 Rs	5	4	6	15	15%
31000-40000 Rs	7	6	5	18	18%
41000-60000Rs	10	8	4	22	22%
61000-70000Rs	7	6	2	15	15%
71000 above Rs	10	8	2	20	20%
Total	42	34	24	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 3, it is found that the highest number of respondents (22%) fall under the income group of Rs. 41,000–60,000, followed by 20% earning above Rs. 71,000. This indicates that middle- and higher-income groups are more inclined towards online shopping as they have better purchasing power. Amazon performs slightly better among higher-income groups, while Flipkart maintains balanced usage.

4. Residential Place.

Table No.4: Residence- Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Urban	15	12	5	32	32%
Semi-Urban	14	13	10	37	37%
Rural	13	9	9	31	31%
Total	42	34	24	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 4, it is clearly seen that 37% of respondents belong to semi-urban areas, followed by urban (32%) and rural (31%). This shows that online shopping is not limited to cities but has spread widely across semi-urban and rural areas. The growth of internet access has contributed to this trend.

5. Customer usage Pattern

Table No.5: Customer Usage Patter - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Daily	7	10	3	20	20%
Weekly	15	13	7	35	35%

Monthly	12	9	9	30	30%
Rarely	8	5	2	15	15%
Total	42	37	21	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 5, it is observed that most respondents (35%) use e-commerce platforms on a weekly basis, followed by 30% who use them monthly. Only 20% use them daily. This indicates that online shopping is used regularly but not necessarily every day. Flipkart has slightly higher daily usage, showing better engagement with customers.

6. Pricing Satisfaction

Table No.6 : Pricing Satisfaction - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
High	15	20	10	45	45%
Medium	12	10	8	30	30%
Low	5	7	13	25	25%
Total	32	37	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 6, it is found that a majority of respondents (45%) have high satisfaction with pricing. This suggests that customers feel prices are reasonable and competitive. Flipkart has the highest satisfaction level, indicating effective pricing strategies compared to Amazon and Meesho.

7. Discount Satisfaction

Table No.7 : Discount Satisfaction - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
High	14	22	9	45	45%
Medium	12	10	8	30	30%
Low	6	5	14	25	25%
Total	32	37	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 7, it is observed that 45% of respondents have high satisfaction with discounts offered. Discounts play a major role in attracting customers. Flipkart leads in this aspect, providing better offers and deals, while Meesho has comparatively lower satisfaction.

8. Services Satisfaction

Table No.8 : . Services Satisfaction - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
High	16	23	8	47	47%
Medium	10	9	11	30	30%
Low	6	5	12	23	23%
Total	32	37	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 8, it is clear that 47% of respondents have high satisfaction with service quality. This reflects that most customers are satisfied with delivery, responsiveness, and overall service. Flipkart performs best in service satisfaction, followed by Amazon.

9. Packaging Quality

Table No.9 : Packaging Quality - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Good	20	18	7	45	45%
Average	8	10	12	30	30%

Poor	4	9	12	25	25%
Total	32	37	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 9, it is observed that 45% of respondents rate packaging quality as good, while 30% rate it as average. Amazon slightly leads in good packaging, indicating better handling and safety of products. Flipkart also performs well but slightly behind Amazon.

10. Product Category Preference

Table No.10. Product Category Preference of Respondents.

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Electronics	10	12	3	25	25%
Clothing	8	10	7	25	25%
Home Appliances	6	7	2	15	15%
Beauty Products	5	6	4	15	15%
Book	3	4	1	8	8%
Others	3	5	4	12	12%
Total	35	44	21	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 10, it is found that electronics and clothing (25% each) are the most preferred product categories among respondents. This shows that customers mainly use e-commerce for essential and trendy items. Flipkart has higher preference across most categories, especially electronics and clothing.

11. Return and Refund

Table No.11. Return and Refund - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Easy	14	18	8	40	40%
Moderate	12	10	9	31	31%
Difficult	9	6	14	29	29%
Total	35	34	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 11, it is observed that 40% of respondents find the return and refund process easy, while 31% consider it moderate. This indicates that most platforms provide acceptable return policies. Flipkart stands out with the highest "easy" responses, showing better customer-friendly policies.

12. Customer Support.

Table No.12 Customer Support - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Good	14	18	8	40	40%
Average	12	10	9	31	31%
Poor	9	6	14	29	29%
Total	35	34	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 12, it is clear that 40% of respondents rate customer support as good. This indicates that many customers receive proper assistance when issues arise. Flipkart again leads in customer support, providing quicker and more effective service.

13. Problem Faced

Table No.13 Problem Faced - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Late Delivery	10	8	12	30	30%
Poor Quality	9	7	11	27	27%
Payment Issues	6	5	7	18	18%
No issues	10	14	1	25	25%
Total	35	34	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 13, it is found that late delivery (30%) and poor quality (27%) are the major problems faced by respondents. However, 25% of respondents reported no issues. Flipkart has the highest number of "no issues," indicating relatively better performance compared to Amazon and Meesho.

14 .Overall Satisfaction

Table No.14. Overall Satisfaction - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
High	15	18	7	40	40%
Medium	12	10	9	31	31%
Low	8	6	15	29	29%
Total	35	34	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 14, it is observed that 40% of respondents have high overall satisfaction, while 31% have medium satisfaction. This shows that most customers are generally satisfied with e-commerce services. Flipkart ranks highest in overall satisfaction, followed by Amazon.

15. Recommendation

Table No.15. Recommendation - Wise Distribution of Respondents

Variable	Amazon	Flipkart	Meesho	Total	Percentage
Yes	22	25	13	60	60%
NO	13	9	18	40	40%
Total	35	34	31	100	100%

Source : Authors' calculation based on primary data

From Table 15, it is clear that a majority of respondents (60%) are willing to recommend these platforms to others. This reflects a positive customer perception towards online shopping. Flipkart has the highest recommendation rate, followed by Amazon, while Meesho has more negative responses.

7. Findings

The present study on customer perception towards online marketing in e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho in Thiruvavur District reveals several important insights based on the analysis of collected data. Firstly, the study shows that younger consumers play a dominant role in online shopping. A majority of respondents belong to the age group of 21–30 years, followed by those below 20 years. This indicates that youth are more comfortable with digital technology, smartphones, and internet usage, which increases their participation in online shopping. Older age groups show comparatively lower involvement, mainly due to limited familiarity with technology.

Secondly, with regard to occupation, students form the largest group of respondents, followed by private employees. This clearly indicates that individuals who are more exposed to digital platforms and modern lifestyles are more likely to engage in e-commerce activities. People engaged in agriculture and business also participate, but to a lesser extent. The income analysis reveals that middle- and higher-income groups are more actively involved in online shopping. Respondents earning between Rs. 41,000 and Rs. 60,000 form the largest segment, followed by those earning above Rs. 71,000. This suggests that higher purchasing power influences online buying behaviour, as these groups can afford a wider range of products and are

attracted by offers and convenience. The study also highlights that online shopping is widely spread across different residential areas. A significant portion of respondents belongs to semi-urban areas, followed by urban and rural regions. This shows that e-commerce is no longer limited to cities but has expanded into rural and semi-urban areas due to improved internet connectivity and smartphone usage. In terms of usage frequency, most respondents prefer shopping on a weekly basis, followed by monthly usage. Daily usage is comparatively lower, indicating that online shopping is a regular but need-based activity rather than a daily habit. Pricing plays a crucial role in influencing customer perception. A majority of respondents express high satisfaction with pricing, indicating that e-commerce platforms provide competitive and reasonable prices. Among the three platforms, Flipkart shows slightly higher satisfaction in pricing strategies. Similarly, discounts and offers are major motivating factors for customers. Many respondents report high satisfaction with discounts, which attract them to shop online. Flipkart again performs better in this aspect, as it provides frequent deals and promotional offers. Service quality is another important factor affecting customer perception. Most respondents express high satisfaction with the services provided, including delivery, responsiveness, and user experience. Flipkart ranks highest in service satisfaction, followed by Amazon. Packaging quality is generally rated as good by most respondents. Amazon performs slightly better in this area, indicating stronger handling and safety measures during delivery. Proper packaging helps in reducing product damage and increases customer trust. Regarding product preferences, electronics and clothing are the most popular categories among customers. This shows that consumers mainly use e-commerce platforms for both essential and fashion-related purchases. Flipkart records higher preference in most product categories. The return and refund process is considered easy by a significant number of respondents. This indicates that e-commerce platforms have developed customer-friendly policies. Flipkart stands out with better performance in return and refund services. Customer support services are rated as good by many respondents, showing that customers receive assistance when needed. However, there is still scope for improvement, especially for platforms like Meesho, which shows comparatively lower satisfaction levels. The study also identifies common problems faced by customers. Late delivery and poor product quality are the major issues reported. These problems negatively affect customer satisfaction and trust. However, a notable percentage of respondents report no issues, indicating overall acceptable service levels. In terms of overall satisfaction, most respondents express a positive attitude towards e-commerce platforms. Flipkart ranks highest in overall satisfaction, followed by Amazon, while Meesho lags slightly behind due to

issues related to quality and delivery. Finally, the majority of respondents are willing to recommend these platforms to others. This reflects a strong positive perception towards online marketing and e-commerce services. Flipkart receives the highest recommendation, indicating better customer experience and satisfaction. Overall, the study concludes that customer perception towards online marketing in e-commerce is largely positive. Factors such as pricing, discounts, service quality, and convenience play a major role in influencing customer satisfaction. While Flipkart leads in most aspects, Amazon maintains strong performance in quality and reliability, and Meesho attracts customers with its affordability. Continuous improvement in service quality, delivery, and product standards will further enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty.

8. Suggestions

Customer Perception Towards Online Marketing in Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho, the following suggestions are offered to improve Customer Satisfaction and overall service Quality.

- Firstly, e-commerce platforms should focus on improving product quality, especially in the case of Meesho. Many customers have reported dissatisfaction due to poor-quality products. Ensuring strict quality checks and reliable sellers will help in building customer trust and reducing complaints.
- Secondly, delivery performance should be enhanced across all platforms. Late delivery has been identified as one of the major problems faced by customers. Companies should strengthen their logistics and supply chain systems to ensure timely delivery, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas.
- Thirdly, customer support services need further improvement. Although a significant number of respondents are satisfied, there are still many who face difficulties in resolving issues. Providing quick responses, 24/7 support, and effective problem-solving mechanisms will improve customer experience.
- Fourthly, return and refund processes should be made simpler and faster. While many respondents find the process easy, some still experience difficulties. Transparent policies, quicker refunds, and easy return procedures will enhance customer confidence.
- Fifthly, pricing strategies should continue to remain competitive. Customers are highly attracted to affordable pricing and discounts. Platforms like Flipkart have performed well in this area, and others should adopt similar strategies to retain and attract more customers.
- Sixthly, more attractive discounts and promotional offers can be introduced regularly. Seasonal sales, festival offers, and exclusive

deals can increase customer engagement and encourage repeat purchases.

- Seventhly, platforms should improve packaging quality, especially for fragile and high-value items. Proper packaging reduces product damage and enhances customer satisfaction. Amazon performs well in this aspect, and other platforms can adopt similar practices.
- Eighthly, awareness programs should be conducted to educate customers about online shopping features such as secure payments, return policies, and order tracking. This is particularly important for customers in rural areas who are still adapting to digital platforms.
- Ninthly, e-commerce companies should focus on improving website and app usability. A user-friendly interface, easy navigation, and fast-loading pages will provide a better shopping experience and attract more users.
- Finally, companies should regularly collect customer feedback and take necessary actions to improve their services. Understanding customer expectations and addressing their problems will help in building long-term relationships and increasing customer loyalty.

9. Conclusion

The present study on customer perception towards online marketing in e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho in Thiruvavur District clearly reveals that online shopping has become an essential part of modern customer behaviour. The growth of internet access, smartphone usage, and digital awareness has significantly influenced customers to shift from traditional shopping methods to online platforms. From the overall analysis, it is understood that most respondents have a positive perception towards e-commerce services. Factors such as convenience, time-saving, wide product availability, and attractive pricing play a major role in influencing customer decisions. Among the three platforms studied, Flipkart emerges as the most preferred platform by the majority of respondents. This is mainly due to its effective pricing strategies, better discounts, strong customer support, and higher overall satisfaction levels. Flipkart has performed consistently well in key areas such as service quality, return and refund policies, and customer engagement, which has increased its popularity among users. Amazon, on the other hand, is recognized for its high product quality, reliable delivery system, and excellent packaging standards. Customers trust Amazon for purchasing quality products and safe delivery, especially for high-value items. Although Amazon performs strongly in terms of reliability and global standards, it is slightly less preferred compared to Flipkart in terms of pricing and

offers, which are key factors influencing customer choice in this study. Meesho is identified as a budget-friendly platform that attracts customers mainly due to its low pricing and affordability. It is especially popular among price-sensitive customers and small-scale buyers. However, the study indicates that Meesho faces challenges in maintaining consistent product quality and delivery performance. These limitations affect customer satisfaction and reduce its competitiveness compared to Amazon and Flipkart. The study also highlights that younger consumers, particularly students and working professionals, are the most active users of e-commerce platforms. Middle- and higher-income groups show greater involvement in online shopping due to their purchasing power. Additionally, the expansion of e-commerce into semi-urban and rural areas shows that online shopping is no longer limited to urban regions. Despite the overall positive perception, certain issues such as late delivery, poor product quality, and occasional payment problems still exist. Addressing these issues is essential for improving customer trust and long-term satisfaction. Platforms must focus on strengthening logistics, ensuring quality control, and enhancing customer support services. In conclusion, while all three platforms contribute significantly to the growth of e-commerce, Flipkart stands out as the most preferred platform among customers in Thiruvavur District due to its balanced performance in pricing, service quality, and customer satisfaction. Amazon maintains a strong position in terms of quality and reliability, while Meesho appeals to customers seeking low-cost products. Continuous improvement in service delivery, product standards, and customer experience will further strengthen customer perception and ensure sustainable growth in the e-commerce sector.

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